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TrialsNet: TRials supported by Smart Networks beyond 5G

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www.trialsnet.eu

PROJECT COMPLETION

Welcome to the latest edition of the TrialsNet newsletter!

As the project concluded, we are proud to share an important recognition that stands as a highlight of our journey. TrialsNet has been recognized among the top 10 Key Achievements of the SNS JU for 2025 - a testament to the dedication and innovation of our entire team. This milestone goes beyond technology, it paves the way for safer, more immersive live events: TrialsNet's network-enabled approach shows how Beyond-5G (B5G) can transform public safety and entertainment at large gatherings, opening up exciting new possibilities ([news](#)).

This special issue presents the platform and network solutions developed and implemented by TrialsNet, reflecting the outcome of comprehensive research efforts and joint engagement throughout the project. The extensive validation results are highlighted, drawn from an impressive 78 trials that engaged thousands of end-users and collected a KPI data lake of approximately 850 measurements. Breakthrough innovations are shared, encompassing the key project's technical innovations, the pioneering results achieved through the Open Call sub-projects, and the innovative process for the development and assessment of Key Value Indicators (KVI). Strategic insights into exploitation and business models are presented, offering an in-depth perspective on the project's approach to value creation and sustainability. Furthermore, it features highlights from cluster workshops and other major project milestones, underscoring the collaborative efforts and significant achievements realized throughout the course of the project.

FINAL PLATFORMS AND NETWORK SOLUTIONS

TrialsNet WP2 carried out the design, integration, and deployment of advanced 5G and B5G network and platform solutions across several European clusters. Its work established the end-to-end infrastructures that enabled large-scale, realistic trials in domains such as transportation, safety, eHealth, emergency response, and cultural experiences. WP2 translated the functional requirements coming from the use-case work packages into fully operational network deployments, combining commercial, private, and experimental infrastructures. These deployments covered technologies from 3GPP Rel-15 to Rel-17, including NSA and SA architectures, sub-6 GHz setups, and extensive 26 GHz mmWave installations, all validated under real field conditions.

WP2 also took care of the onboarding and integration of 24 Open Call sub-projects, extending the project's footprint with new sites and additional private and experimental networks. This validated the openness of the TrialsNet approach and allowed to test new capabilities such as UAV connectivity, advanced positioning, and mission-critical communication.

Beyond infrastructure, WP2 finalized key horizontal and vertical innovations, including Zero-touch Service Management, Digital Twin-enabled optimization, AI-based

diagnostics, and automated slice orchestration. These solutions were validated through measurable KPIs, demonstrating improvements in latency, energy efficiency, resource utilization, and service continuity.

This work allowed WP2 to directly contribute to emerging 6G standardization efforts by providing field-validated insights on autonomous, scalable, and energy-aware

management frameworks, eventually validating the project role in shaping next-generation mobile architectures.

VALIDATION RESULTS

In the project, a total of 22 trials were conducted for the 13 core use cases, in the fields of Infrastructure, Transportation, and Security & Safety (ITSS), eHealth & Emergency (eHE) and Culture, Tourism & Entertainment (CTE). The trials engaged almost 600 users, with using of almost 400 devices and equipment, with measured KPIs and KVIs meeting expectations, thus confirming their success. In the context of Open Call sub-projects, a total of 56 trials were conducted for 24 Open Call sub-projects. The trials engaged almost 3000 users, with using of almost 1000 devices and equipment.

The results collectively illustrate how TrialsNet trials were distributed across infrastructure categories, domains, and technologies by showing that most trials (around 60%) relied on commercial infrastructure, while about 37% were conducted on private and experimental systems. Domain-wise, the ITSS domain hosted the majority of commercial and private deployments, whereas the eHE domain had the largest share of experimental trials. This balance highlights the project's effort to test both stable commercial systems and more innovative experimental infrastructures. Also, results show that newer releases (Rel. 16 and Rel. 17) account for about half of all trials, reflecting the project's focus on forward-looking technologies. At the same time, Rel. 15 was still present in about 50% of trials, maintaining continuity with earlier standards. ITSS concentrated most Rel. 15 and Rel. 17 deployments, while Rel. 16 was dominant in the eHE domain.

Furthermore, trials used both below-6GHz and above-6GHz frequency bands, depending on domain requirements: wide-area domains favored lower bands for coverage, while

localized domains like eHE tested higher bands for speed and capacity. Finally, coverage types were split between outdoor (50%), indoor (35%), and mixed deployments (15%), while domain scale ranged from localized (eHE) to wide-area (ITSS and CTE). More than 75% of trials involved external users such as students, security, and medical staff, with fewer than 25% limited to project personnel due to safety or access constraints. Device diversity was also significant, ranging from consumer devices like smartphones and VR headsets to advanced tools such as drones, robots, and prosthetics.

KPI - TrialsNet performed the evaluation of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) across diverse use cases to assess real-world network performance. The use cases primarily relied on commercial infrastructure for deployments, while private networks implemented 5G Rel. 17. Open Call trials, executed later in the project, showed a higher reliance on commercial networks, reflecting the growing maturity of 5G infrastructure.

The KPI validation results revealed that throughput and latency remain the most critical KPIs to satisfy. While downlink and uplink throughput per user achieved partial validation in large-scale trials due to real-world constraints, latency requirements were consistently met thanks to prior tuning during tests. The most demanding scenarios involved real-time video streaming, which drove stringent requirements for bandwidth, latency, and reliability, as for the “Smart Crowd Monitoring” and “Immersive Fan Engagement”. Emergency and industrial use cases, such as the “Mass Casualty Incident” use case, imposed extreme reliability and localization accuracy requirements.

Open Call trials confirmed similar trends. Use cases like “5G-enabled Secure Surveillance System” and “Beyond 5G Football Stadium” highlighted the need for ultra-high throughput and low latency, while applications in healthcare and autonomous transport stressed reliability and availability. Across all trials, real-time video applications dominated performance demands, and future networks must adopt end-to-end network slicing and strict QoS guarantees to meet these requirements. Latency reduction below 10 ms remains a major challenge, requiring innovations beyond the radio access network.

In addition to technical validation, TrialsNet published the collected KPI [datasets](#) on Zenodo and contributed to the SNS JU Metadata Registry System to enhance data discoverability and quality. Ultimately, TrialsNet demonstrated that, while 5G can support many advanced applications, achieving the stringent requirements of emerging use cases will necessitate scalable infrastructure, robust QoS mechanisms, and innovative solutions for ultra-low latency and high reliability.

KVI – The project established a simple and comprehensive framework for conducting KVI assessment activities which was applied across all trials within the project and its sub-projects. The analysis of KVI is reliable due to the relatively large number of participants during trials, the use of a common and simple framework for all trials, and the careful selection of KVI questionnaires. In addition, a 1–5 Likert scale was applied uniformly across trials. The findings reveal a strong emphasis on the social value category, with trial participants providing consistently positive feedback on the deployed technologies. Overall, the results demonstrate a positive perception among end users regarding the impact of TrialsNet. In particular, the high proportion of KVIs scoring above 4 indicates strong endorsement of the project’s contribution to societal, economic, and

environmental benefits. These outcomes highlight the relevance of the selected UCs and the effectiveness of the implemented solutions in supporting sustainability objectives. The results further highlight the significant societal impact of the TrialsNet UCs, emphasizing the importance of social dimensions in the development and adoption of emerging technologies, i.e. B5G. The trials clearly show that societal factors play a central role in shaping user acceptance, perceived value, and long-term technological integration.

KEI INNOVATIONS OF THE PROJECT

The TrialsNet project has successfully concluded its comprehensive 3-stage innovation process, identifying 15 key breakthroughs that bridge the gap between current 5G infrastructure and the future of 6G technology. By testing these innovations across clusters in Italy, Spain, Romania, and Greece, the project has moved beyond theoretical research into practical, real-world applications. This process involved rigorous screening to ensure each innovation provides measurable technical, societal, and economic value, focusing on areas like ultra-reliable connectivity and intelligent automation.

A significant portion of these innovations focuses on transforming public services and safety. Notable achievements include the deployment of 5G-controlled security robots for crowd monitoring and a Metaverse Control Room that allows emergency responders to coordinate in a shared virtual space during crises. Furthermore, the project has pioneered life-changing healthcare solutions, such as delocalizing the heavy computing power required for advanced prosthetics to the cloud. This allows for lighter, more intuitive artificial limbs that can "see" and react to their environment in real-time using ultra-low latency 5G networks.

Beyond technical hardware, TrialsNet is setting new standards for how networks are managed, introducing ZeroTouch autonomous management and AI-driven energy orchestrators that can reduce network power consumption by up to 20%. Meanwhile, in the cultural sector, TrialsNet leads the way on how cultural heritage is experienced, through immersive AR/VR guides and mixed-reality experiences - such as those trialed in Turin's automotive and art museums - redefining how the public engages with history. As 6G moves from vision to reality, these 15 innovations provide a solid foundation for a more connected, sustainable, and inclusive European digital landscape. A detailed list of the identified innovations and their implications, together with a complete description of the used methodology, is available in [Deliverable 6.3](#).

EXPLOITATION ACTIVITIES

The exploitation activities transformed technical achievements and the results and reflection of the trials into concrete business opportunities through a structured methodology designed to bring the solutions to market. The work focused on three clear objectives: establishing robust frameworks for business model development, co-creating market-oriented exploitation plans for each use case, and uncovering new collaborative opportunities among partners. This approach ensured that every use case benefited from

tailored strategies aligned with its specific technical readiness, market position, and partnership dynamics.

Between February and June 2025, TID conducted dedicated workshops with each use case team, creating spaces for collaborative thinking and strategic refinement. Partners worked with Business Model Canvas templates to map out their business fundamentals, from value propositions and customer segments to revenue streams and key partnerships. The sessions went beyond product development and planning, focusing on Joint Exploitation Plans that identified how partners could combine their strengths and resources to build more stable and sustainable ventures together. Total Addressable Market assessments complemented this work, helping teams estimate and understand the full revenue potential of their innovations.

The methodology proved successful in bridging the gap between technological capability and market reality. Comprehensive reports were generated for each use case, documenting business model canvases, joint exploitation plans, and monetization strategies. The most representative cases were selected based on criteria such as interdependent partnership structures, revenue diversification potential, and clear go-to-market pathways. This systematic approach ensures that TrialsNet innovations continue to deliver economic, operational, and societal value well beyond the project's conclusion, with clear roadmaps for commercialization and sustainable growth.

CLUSTER WORKSHOPS

During this last period, the TrialsNet clusters organised several workshops and communication events to present the use cases, show the technical progress, and engage with local stakeholders. Each workshop focused on the solutions deployed within the cluster and allowed participants to see live demonstrations, discuss lessons learned, and understand how 5G/B5G networks support real operational scenarios. Alongside the workshops, the project team participated in conferences, seminars, and industry exhibitions to showcase the results to a broader audience.

Madrid Cluster: The Madrid cluster focused on the Smart Crowd Monitoring and Immersive Fan Engagement use cases. These demonstrations showed how AI-based analytics, robots, and 5G connectivity can be used to improve situational awareness during large events. The [Madrid Cluster Workshop](#) took place on 8 September 2025 at the 5TONIC facilities and allowed visitors to see the millimetre-wave infrastructure used in the trial and observe live measurements of the system's behaviour. Attendees experienced the real-time monitoring system used in the Movistar

Arena trial, including video streams processed through the 5G SA network and the integrated AI pipeline. Communication activities of the cluster included participation in the WeAR Industry Fair in Bilbao, EuCNC 2025, and multiple public trial demonstrations, ensuring strong visibility for the Madrid cluster at national and European level.

Iași Cluster: In Iași, the TrialsNet cluster continued working on the Smart Crowd Monitoring and Smart Traffic Management use cases, focusing on real-time analytics and city-level applications. The Iași Cluster Workshop took place on 30 October 2025 at the TUIASI 5G Lab and presented live demonstrations of both use cases. Participants observed the full data flow from cameras through Nokia Fastmile 5G connectivity into the local edge servers hosting the AI modules. The workshop also included sessions by the Open Call projects, who presented complementary solutions for mobility, safety and

adaptive control. Additional dissemination for the Iași cluster included participation in TECHNOVERS 2025, the VNPT 5G Exploration workshop, and the public demonstration event in May 2025, which attracted representatives from local institutions, academia and industry.

Athens Cluster: Focused on advanced robotics, digital-twin supervision, airport automation, ehealth and emergency for quicker and more efficient triage, pre-hospital treatment and evacuation in populated areas, and infrastructure inspection through the UC2, UC3, UC6, UC11, UC13 use cases, the [Athens Cluster Workshop](#) was held on 5 November 2025 at Athens International Airport (AIA).

The event gathered airport operators, municipal authorities and technology partners and included demonstrations of inspection robots, AGVs, multi-sensor fusion workflows and the digital twin platforms supervising them. The workshop also hosted Open Call use cases that showcased autonomous operation, video analytics and secure surveillance.

Further dissemination activities from the cluster included contributions at the DAEM Digital Governance event, EuCNC 2025, and multiple field demonstrations at AIA and Technopolis.

Turin Cluster: The [Turin Cluster Workshop](#) demonstrated how augmented reality and 5G-enabled applications can support tourism and the cultural sector. It took place on 18 September 2025, in collaboration with the CTE NEXT initiative “Torino Easy to Visit: Innovation in Culture and Tourism”, and presented the AR applications deployed in Valentino Park and partner museums. Attendees included museum representatives, local SMEs, technology integrators, and public authorities. The workshop highlighted the value of connected immersive services in cultural digitalisation strategies, and gave space also to the use cases funded through the Open Call, enreaching the event with a wide range of technology demos. Further dissemination activities from the cluster also included participation in regional innovation events, conference demonstrations, and communication actions linked to Turin’s role as European Capital of Innovation.

Pisa Cluster: This cluster specially focused on eHealth, including UC7, 8 and 9. The [Pisa Cluster Workshop](#) took place on November 4th, 2025, at the CNR Research Area in Pisa, and was co-organized by CNR, Ericsson, TIM, Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna, and IIT. The event brought together local stakeholder, including telecommunications providers, vendors, universities, research centers, and healthcare professionals. It had a special focus on how the achieved results can be further exploited and valorized beyond the project’s conclusion. Participants also had the opportunity to experience live demonstrations of the eHealth trials developed within the project, including the Open Call sub-project COM05, which further enriched the technological scope of the event. Overall, the event fostered dialogue between the technological and clinical domains, showcasing how 5G and next-generation network technologies are transforming healthcare delivery and biomedical innovation. Participants discussed real-world applications, future opportunities for eHealth, and strategies for collaboration and exploitation.

The achievements of this cluster have received significant attention in the media, reinforcing Pisa’s role as a strategic hub for innovation and research in the field of eHealth and advanced network technologies.

PROJECT KEY REMARKS TOWARDS 6G DEFINITION

The analysis of the TrialsNet trial activities done in Sec 8 of D6.3 unveiled how the project use cases are fully consistent with the 6G service categories currently being consolidated within 3GPP SA1 TR 22.870 and aligned with the broader IMT 2030 framework. By engaging diverse verticals across transportation, eHealth, cultural experiences, and industrial automation, the project ensured that each use case exercised functionalities that map naturally to 3GPP categories such as Integrated Sensing and Communication, Immersive Communication, Ubiquitous Connectivity, AI driven Services, and Industry or Verticals. The systematic mapping methodology, based on feature analysis, KPI and KVI targets, and functional alignment to TR clauses, demonstrated that all core TrialsNet use cases can be positioned within the emerging 6G taxonomy, with several use cases spanning multiple categories because of their multi domain characteristics.

Beyond establishing this alignment, the trials provided tangible insights into the network performance and functional gaps that must be addressed for 6G systems to support these applications at scale. Large scale deployments revealed that many stringent requirements, especially those involving uplink throughput, latency, and tight jitter control, can only be satisfied today through bespoke or enhanced infrastructures that rely on dedicated coverage, optimized backhaul, or localized edge compute. While these setups enabled successful demonstrations in XR based cultural experiences, medical use cases, and cooperative robotics, they also highlight the limitations of current commercial networks, which remain primarily optimized for downlink centric services. Ensuring economic sustainability, improving uplink capacity, and providing native support for deterministic communication therefore emerge as key priorities for 6G architectures aiming to deliver carrier grade performance for the next generation of interactive, intelligent, and safety critical applications.

TRIALSNET INFORMATION

If you are looking for further info about the project structure, consortium, the different use cases, as well as news and contacts, the [project website](#) is the place to go. The project deliverables, publications, together with other dissemination and communication material, are available on the corresponding [website section](#).

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